

Africa's Coastline Long-Term Monitoring Using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques

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Abstract—In this paper we explore the potential of Digital Earth Africa (DE Africa) coastlines products for the calculation of one of the Erosion Warning Indicator Namely Long-Term shoreline trend indicator. The parameter is calculated and estimated based on the relationship between the cross-shore annual shoreline positions and the annual observation. DE Africa provide information related on the coastal dynamics for the period of 23 years. Here, we analyse the Digital Earth Africa (DE Africa) coastlines products V0.4.2 by performing the regression modelling to calculate the long-term shoreline trend indicator. The methodological approach proposed allowed to extract the long-term trend of shoreline changes at continental, national and local scales. The results indicated that the Africa's coastline have been both retreating and advancing. Such processes impacted the African population of about 709775 living within 1 km of the shoreline and low-lying flat areas.

Keywords—*Earth observation, satellite images, coastal erosion, Digital shoreline analysis system, DSAS.*

I. INTRODUCTION

With the current changes into the climate system and their impacts in the coastal areas, the processes which influence the shape and dynamics of the shoreline and the coastline will be further exacerbated. Coastal erosion is one of these processes [1], it is a natural phenomenon which is also further impacted by human activities [2]. For example, in the West Africa [3,4], coastal areas host about one third of the region's population and generate 56% of its GD. Among the 54 African countries, 36 are coastal. With this situation you can image the importance of the Africa's coastline, especially by considering the fact that African megacities with over 10 million inhabitants are expected to be developed in coastal areas by 2050 [5]. Also, it has been observed that the African population will be doubled in the next 25 years and reaching 2.5 billion people [6]. With this in mind, the health and efficiency of coastal areas is increasingly becoming fundamental to sustain their socio-economic practices. The question is: how can we monitor these coastal areas to provide policy and decision makers with tools to better be prepared and combat the future natural cotastrophes for a sustainable management of the Africa's coasts? For decades, Earth Observation (EO) satellite remote sensing programs such as Landsat and Copernicus Sentinels have been gathering information about the Earth's surface, water and atmosphere. Such information is very useful for the understanding of the past, the present and the future states of the coastal environments through analyses and modeling of the shoreline. EO satellite remote sensing technology has transformed coastal science from a "data-poor" field into a "data-rich" field [7]. Christofi et al. [8] reviewed the open-access remote sensing technology in shoreline detection and coastal erosion monitoring through the use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), and Ground Truth Data (GTD). According

to the authors, these technologies offer heightened spatial and temporal resolutions, which are key elements in the effective and efficient tracking of complex shoreline change patterns. Bishop-Taylor et al. [9] used three decades of Landsat imagery to Map the Australia's dynamic oastline. The authors concluded that the methodological approach proposed could be reproduced and used to any coastal region globally with access to a sufficient multi-temporal satellite data from medium resolution satellites such as Landsat and Sentinel-2. The study conducted by Ankrah et al. [10] reviewed the shoreline change and coastal erosion in western Africa. According to the authors, the shoreline changes and coastal erosion research in West Africa has progressed substantially, reflecting the increasing concerns of scientists in the region with no studies in countries such as Côte d'Ivoire, Sierra Leone, and Mauritania. Digital Earth Africa program was implemented to takes advantage of years of Landsat satellite data and produce products and provide services related to water resources and flood risks management; agriculture and food security; land degradation and coastline erosion; and services related to urbanisation [11,12]. The aim of this study is to evaluate the potential of DE Africa coastlines products version V0.4.2 [13] for the calculation of the long-term shoreline trend indicator. Conventional methods of monitoring the coastline erosion require resource-intensive, field surveys and they are time-consuming and they can be hazardous. In addition, aerial photography and LiDAR survey methods are expensive and require for frequent revisits for scientific studies. In this regard, we used the DE Africa coastlines products which offer LTM information tailored to land quality and coastline change monitoring along the African continent. The methodological approach proposed allowed to extract the Erosion Warning Indicator (EWI)[14].

This study represents the first application of DE Africa coastline products for the long-term trend assessment of shoreline changes at continental, national and local scales. By integrating satellite-derived shoreline metrics with expert-wise interpretation, we propose a transferable approach for EWI, namely long-term shoreline trend indicator, for the analysis of shoreline changes at continental, national and local scales. The use of annual shoreline rates from 2000–2023 adds a temporal dimension often lacking in conventional studies, allowing for the identification of long-term trends relevant for local planning.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this study, DE Africa coastlines products for the period of 23 years were analysed to evaluate the shoreline changes at continental, national and local scales. The multi-scale analysis was conducted by adopting the Digital Shoreline Analysis System [15] (DSAS)-type methodological approach to extract the EWI [14]. While EWI are mainly five, here we intend to explore the long-term shoreline trend indicator.

1) Digital Earth Africa Coastlines Products Description

The DE Africa coastlines products as shown in (Tab. 1) are continental datasets from 2000 to 2023 [16,17]. They include annual shorelines and rates of coastal change along the entire African coastline. The products combine satellite data from the DE Africa program with tidal modelling to map the typical location of the coastline at mean sea level for each year. These products have been generated following the same procedures as the Digital Earth Australia coastline products [9]. Their accuracy and performance have been evaluated by The Centre de Suivi Ecologique, Dakar, with the member countries of the WACA/ORLOA network. In each country, test sites have been selected depending on the size of the portion of the coast, the availability of reference data and metadata associated with each type of data. With imagery for each country having a consistent accuracy of 5 m [16]. DE Africa coastline products are grouped into two shapefile categories, polylines for the African annual shorelines that represent the median or ‘most representative’ position of the shoreline at approximately 0 m Above Mean Sea Level for each year since 2000 to 2023; and points for the African shoreline rates of change statistics which are point datasets providing robust rates of coastal change for every 30 m along Africa’s coastlines. DE Africa coastlines products enable the trends of coastal erosion and growth to be examined annually at both local and continental scale. They also allow patterns of coastal change to be mapped historically and updated regularly as data continues to be acquired.

TABLE I. DIGITAL EARTH AFRICA COASTLINES PRODUCT DATASETS DESCRIPTIONS

Specification	Descriptions
Cell size - X (meters)	30
Cell size - Y (meters)	30
Coordinate reference system	ESPG :6933
Temporal resolution	Annual
Temporal range	2000 - 2023
Parent dataset	Landsat Collection 2 Surface Reflectance
Update frequency	Annual
Update latency	6 months from end of previous year
Product types	Annual coastlines; Rate of change statistics
Product names	coastlines_v0.4.2_shorelines_anual; coastlines_v0.4.2_rates_of_change
Data types	Shapefiles : polylines and points

2) Coastline Dynamic analyses

Beside information provided by DE Africa coastlines products, DSAS-type methodological approach was adopted to compute, extract and analyze the coastal dynamics parameters. While, DSAS has previously been used by many authors [18, 19] examining and evaluating the shoreline changes, by the knowledge of the author, this current study is the first of its kind conducted to analyzing the shoreline dynamics from 2000 to 2023 conducted using DSAS-type analyses to examine parameters such as annual shoreline distances, Shoreline Change Envelope (SCE), Net Shoreline Movement (NSM), Linear Regression Rate (LRR) and End Point Rate (EPR) [20]. The methodology was implemented as presented in Figs. 1-4; and computed following equations 1-4. Here, LRR represents the long-term shoreline trend indicator assumed as the EWI [14].

Fig. 1. Methodology used to explore the Digital Earth Africa Coastlines products for the calculation of Erosion Warning Long-Term Shoreline Trend Indicator. For each transect, LRR was computed by linearly regressing annual shoreline cross-shore positions against yearly observations as presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Map depicting the cross-shore intersections of the annual shoreline positions obtained for the period of 23 years along the point 60 located on the coast of John Obey Beach, in Sierra Leone as shown in Fig. 1. The cross-shore distance between each annual shoreline and the 2023 shoreline was computed and used to calculate the long-term shoreline trend indicator as presented in Fig. 3.

$$y = amx + bm \quad (1)$$

$$bm = \frac{n \sum_i x_i y_i - \sum_i x_i \sum_i y_i}{n \sum_i x_i^2 - (\sum_i x_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$am = \frac{\sum_i x_i^2 \sum_i y_i - \sum_i x_i \sum_i x_i y_i}{n \sum_i x_i^2 - (\sum_i x_i)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$NSM = (do - di) \quad (4)$$

$$EPR = \frac{(do - di)}{(to - ti)} \quad (5)$$

where am represents the slope of the regression line for the intersection points on the m th profile LRR, bm is the intercept of the regression line for the intersection points, xi is the x-coordinate value of the intersection point on the m profile at moment i , yi is the distance between the intersection point and the baseline on the m th profile at moment i (y-coordinate value), and n represents the number of intersection points between the profile and the shoreline [21-30]. di is distance of the oldest shoreline, do is distance of the recent shoreline, ti is shoreline date (time) of the oldest shoreline to is shoreline date (time) of the recent shoreline.

Fig. 3. Illustration of LRR calculation conducted using cross-shore annual shoreline distances for the period of 23 years. This is an example for the point 60 as shown in Fig. 1. LRR is calculated by considering all the annual shoreline positions, here the slope of the line equals the rate of change (- 0.06 m/yr). In addition to the LRR, the DSAS-type approach analyses revealed values of the NSM of about 3.15 m, the value of EPR of about 0.137 m/year obtained by considering the slope of the line between the cross-shore positions of the oldest annual shoreline (2000) and the most recent annual shoreline (2023), and the value of SCE of about 15.4 m.

Fig. 1-3 present an example of the proposed methodology to evaluate the long-term shoreline trend along the coastline of John Obey Beach located in Sierra Leone. This beach is one of the most affected by anthropologic activities such as sand mining and other which have been contributing extensively to the coastal erosion and environment degradation. For each transect, measurement of the annual shoreline positions was conducted and used for the calculation of LRR and then reported on points for every 30 m along the coastline. Fig. 4 represent the same methodological procedure for the beach of Essaouira located on the western coastline of Morocco where the long-term shoreline trend was computed the same period.

Fig. 4. An other example of illustration for the calculation of Erosion Warning Long-Term Shoreline Trend Indicator which was performed for each transect along the coastline of Essaouira beach located in Morocco.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The calculation of Erosion Warning Long-Term Shoreline Trend Indicator performed for each transect by linearly regressing annual shoreline cross-shore positions against yearly observations using the Digital Earth Africa Coastlines products for a period of 23 years allows for the analysis of shoreline changes at continental (Fig. 5), national (Fig. 6) and local (Fig. 7) scales. The results obtained for the African total mapped shoreline, indicated the African total retreated shoreline of about 7582 km, the African total advanced shoreline of about 8578 km. It is important to note that such changes impacted African population of about 709775 people living within 1 km of the shoreline and low lying flat areas. In addition some case studies indicated that for about 3231km shoreline were mapped along the coastline of Morocco, the shoreline retreated for about 235 km and it advanced for about 191 km. Along the coastline of Namibia, about 1668 km shoreline were mapped; the results indicated a retreat of about 318.6 km and an advancement of about 229.6 km. For Sierra Leone, the total shoreline mapped was about 1205 km, the results indicated that the shoreline retreated for about 177 km and advanced for about 217 km. such changes impacted the population of about 16800 living within 1 km of the shoreline and low-lying flat areas.

Fig. 5. Erosion hotspots identified along the Africa's coastline. They were obtained using Erosion Warning Long-Term Shoreline Trend Indicator analyzed for the period 2000-2023.

Fig. 6. Erosion hotspots identified along the coastline of Morocco. They were obtained using Erosion Warning Long-Term Shoreline Trend Indicator evaluated for the period 2000-2023.

Fig. 7. Erosion hotspots identified along the coastline of Namibia desert. The hotspots were obtained using Erosion Warning Long-Term Shoreline Trend Indicator analyzed for the period 2000-2023.

Although the DE Africa coastlines products are based on medium-resolution, the shoreline positions have been validated to achieve a median horizontal positional accuracy of approximately 5m. This level of accuracy, combined with its consistent multi-temporal coverage, makes the dataset appropriate for regional-scale shoreline change analysis in data-scarce environments. African coastline was selected as a case study due to its high exposure to erosion, rapid urbanization and increasing development pressures [2]. Despite the African coastline importance, the continent lacks long-term, spatially consistent products, offering harmonized multi-temporal coastal erosion analyses. Thus, DE Africa coastlines products reanalysis provides a unique opportunity to address this gap.

IV. LIMITATIONS

This study offers a comprehensive overview of the calculation of the Erosion Warning Indicator, namely long-term shoreline trend indicator, for the analysis of shoreline changes at continental, national and local scales in Africa. Yet, several limitations should be considered. The analyses were based on DE Africa coastlines products, which, despite being calibrated and validated, may present relevant application limitations related to spatial/temporal resolution,

lack of ground-truth data and sensor-specific biases. Further research should explore how the spatial patterns of erosion and accretion relate to regional oceanographic and meteorological drivers, such as wave exposure, prevailing currents and tidal range. Incorporating datasets such as ERA5 wave reanalysis, sediment budgets, or coastal modification records could provide valuable context for interpreting the physical processes underlying shoreline change. Such information would increase the relevance and reduce the impact of data uncertainty on the outcome of the Erosion Warning Indicator.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, DE Africa coastline products were evaluated with the aim of analyzing the shoreline changes for every 30 m spacing along the Africa's coastline. The ability to calculate the rate of change of the shoreline for each 30 m provides a huge opportunity to identify the areas affected by erosion and accretion. This information is beneficial for determining how such geological processes contribute to the Africa's coastal vulnerability. The level of detail offered by this point-based analysis is rarely explored in long-term shoreline trend indicator studies, particularly in the African context. Multi-scale Erosion Warning Long-Term Shoreline Trend Indicator results indicated that the African coastal states have the possibility to use these products monitor shoreline changes at national and local levels. Such information could help implement measure to reduce the number of populations impacted by storm surges and land degradation as the coast are eroding.

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